

Next generation Alkaline Membrane Water Electrolysers with Improved Components and Materials

Draft Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.2)

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www.newely.eu

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0 Summary

This document outlines the plan for the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) of the NEWELY project in accordance with the partners' interests and the signed Grant Agreement. This document, combined with the more detailed Exploitation Plan (planned at M12), provides an overview of the project's undertaken and planned activities for dissemination, communication and exploitation of the knowledge generating during the NEWELY project. This document will be updated periodically during the project's lifetime to tune the D&C actions in accordance with the project results and the exploitation strategy.

1 Introduction

This document outlines the plan for the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) of the NEWELY project in accordance with the partners' interests and the signed Grant Agreement. This document, combined with the more detailed Exploitation Plan (planned at M12), provides an overview of the project's undertaken and planned activities for dissemination, communication and exploitation of the knowledge generating during the NEWELY project.

Communication and dissemination activities aim to raise awareness, attract and engage multiple stakeholders on the project's activities and results. On the one side, communication activities will share general information about the NEWELY project to broad and mixed audiences. On the other hand, dissemination activities will target networks of potential end-users and stakeholders that might be directly interested in exploiting the project results.

The Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan aims to establish a strategy to identify, reach out and engage multiple stakeholders in the hydrogen production sector (industries, research institutes, standardization bodies and governments) and European citizen. The main activities included in the first draft of the D&C Plan are:

- the design of the project visual identity and of the public website to be periodically updated with news on the project;
- publication of dedicated press releases;
- publication of a project brochure, flyer and poster to be used during the dissemination events and workshops;
- publication of scientific papers in journals, proceedings of international conferences and/or workshops;
- presentations at relevant international conferences, events and forums, trade fairs, media channels (e.g. TV, radio) etc.;
- communication via social media (Twitter and LinkedIn);
- organisation of two dissemination workshops;
- organisation of a final dissemination event at the end of the project.

This document will be updated periodically during the project's lifetime to tune the D&C actions in accordance with the project results and the exploitation strategy.

1.1 Definitions

All definitions are reported in the Consortium Agreement (CA) and in the Grant Agreement (GA). Some essential definitions are here complemented:

“Confidential Information” means any and all information that is disclosed or otherwise made available by the disclosing Party to the receiving Party pursuant to the Consortium Agreement including, but not limited to Background, Sideground and/or Foreground:

- financial information, such as but not limited to pricing and customer lists;
- technical information, such as but not limited to research, development, algorithms, procedures, software and know-how;
- business information, such as but not limited to operations, planning, marketing interests and products.

Such information may be disclosed or made available: orally, in written (including but not limited to, fax, e-mail, text messages (SMS)) or machine-readable format or other tangible things including - but not limited - to raw materials, components, models, prototypes, tool or equipment whatsoever or intangible form (including but not limited to visual inspection during any tour of the disclosing Party's facilities or premises).

"Communication" means the promotion of the NEWELY action and its results, by providing targeted information to a multitude audience (including the media and the public / society) in a strategic and effective manner, identifying and setting proper communication objectives using pertinent messages, right medium and means. This means to do proper actions to reach out to society as whole or specific selected audiences (non-specialists) on the NEWELY topic and increasing visibility on how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

"Dissemination" means the disclosure of Foreground by any appropriate means other than that resulting from the formalities for protecting it, and including the publication of Foreground in any medium. In order to maximize the impact of research, enabling the value of results to be potentially wider than the original focus, the results shall be transferred - under shared agreement - to the ones that can best make use of it.

“Exploitation” means the direct or indirect utilisation of Foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service. Direct utilisation is done by the participant owning the Foreground (e.g. through further research or commercial or industrial exploitation in its own activities) while indirect utilisation is done by other parties (e.g. through licensing) under shared agreement.

1.2 Strategic Impact

The NEWELY project will have a significant impact on the work programme topic “FCH-02-4-2019: New Anion Exchange Membrane electrolyzers within the call H2020-JTI-FCH-2019-1” for improving the hydrogen production sector in Europe. In this context, electrolysis plays an important role for hydrogen production from renewable electricity (low carbon pathway) applied on energy storage and grid balancing. Specifically, FCH-02-4-2019 asks for an improvement of Anion Exchange Membrane Water Electrolyser (AEMWE) components, moving the technology from technology readiness level (TRL) 2 to TRL 4 and showing a first small scale working prototype.

The NEWELY project aims to answer to the specific challenge of the call by demonstrating the cost benefit of AEM technology in terms of CAPEX and operating expenditure (OPEX) for hydrogen production. The project plans to develop an innovative AEMWE with tailored polymer structure, optimized ionomer and binder structure, ink-dispersion properties, and coating techniques to fabricate highly efficient and durable electrode packages with improved ionic conductivity.

The results deriving from the NEWELY project are expected to impact on key EU and FCH JU objectives, specifically addressing the following targets, as described in the “Impact” section of the Grant Agreement:

- Increase membrane and ionomer conductivity and stability by using innovative design and structure and components that will lead to a substantial increase on the AEM conductivity up to 50 mS cm^{-1} , while improving the mechanical stability and reducing water uptake and gas crossover;
- Optimize chemical composition and activity of non-PGM electrocatalysts by using microporous layers that will optimize electrocatalyst conductivity, dispersion and utilization in the electrode;
- Improve the cell design by integrating the electrode packages in an innovative stack design based on hydraulic compression technology, that will allow to reach output hydrogen pressure up to 40 bar without mechanically stressing the cell components;
- Validate high performance process for high production to increase the energy efficiency of hydrogen production;
- Validation of long-term durability of stack (at least 2,000 h);
- Create awareness for the potential market deployment of the AEMWE technology;
- Impact on job creation;
- Impact on techno-economic objectives of the FCH JU:
 - increase efficiency and reduce cost of AEMWE;
 - increase efficiency and reduce cost of hydrogen production from renewable sources;
- Impact on operational objectives of the FCH JU:
 - leverage private and public investment in the hydrogen economy;
 - maintain SME participation above 25%;

1.3 Expected results of the D&C plan

The expected outcome of the actions described in this plan aim to improve the visibility and exploitation potential of the NEWELY results, thus supporting the Consortium in achieving the impact expected from the project. Communication and dissemination initiatives will be scheduled in detail on a yearly basis to achieve the objectives, balancing the available resources and considering additional in-kind contribution by each partner.

The success of the D&C Plan will be measured at the end of the project, using the following KPI's:

- a) Number of scientific publications and conference presentations;
- b) Number of activities performed to increase the visibility of the project;
- c) Number of engagements with the project measured through the number of visits to the project website and the number of followers on social media;
- d) Number of distributed communication materials (flyer, brochures, etc.);
- e) Number of published journalistic articles and press releases (at least one/year);
- f) Number of visualisations of the first short video;
- g) Number of participated exhibitions/trade fairs/public events (at least two/year);
- h) Number of organised knowledge-sharing events (eg.: a training seminar, a demo/field visit and a final dissemination event);
- i) Total number of stakeholders engaged for each type of D&C activity.

2 Dissemination and Communication Principles

The main goal of all D&C activities is to maximize the exploitation potential of the knowledge and results deriving from the NEWELY project. To this end, the first step of the D&C plan consists in identifying the groups of stakeholders that can benefit from the achievements of the NEWELY project and the most relevant D&C channels to reach each group. Table 1 summarizes the target stakeholder groups, the key messages to share, the communication channels and the channels that will be used for D&C activities.

Table 1 Stakeholder target groups

	Stakeholder group	Key message	D&C activities	D&C channel
Primary target group	Users of the Electrolyser components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Producers of Electrolysers • Producers of electrolyser components and materials • Customers interested in buying an electrolyser Suppliers of electrochemical components beyond the electrolysis technology such as fuel cells, CO ₂ reduction, batteries, SCRs, chemical production methods	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical properties of materials, components and systems 2. Costs and manufacturing processes 3. Parameter validation and efficiency increase potential 4. Requirements on high performance 	Presentations, handouts, website, social media posts, scientific publications	National and European industry associations, magazines/website, social media, workshop, symposium, conferences and relevant exhibitions
Secondary target group	Users and customers of similar material in another technological context such as mobility, aerospace, filter technology, hydraulic sector	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Show the contribution of the expected material properties to other processes than electrolysis; 2. Material validation 	Presentations, handouts, website, social media posts, scientific publications	Direct contact by partners, workshops and conferences, industry fairs and relevant exhibitions
Tertiary target group	Researchers	Demonstrate the achieved results and share new knowledge generated	Presentations, scientific publications	Scientific conferences, scientific journals
	Policy makers, regulators and international organisations	Technology advancements and role of legislation and standards to support market uptake	Presentations in committees and workshop	Committee meetings, magazines, web site, personal communication by mail

	General public and citizens	Information about the project and future perspectives for a green hydrogen economy	Website post, magazine articles, social media post, presentations	Website, social media, workshops
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D&C activities will be performed constantly during the project. A detailed schedule of the D&C activities will be planned on a yearly basis in order to ensure the maximization of the reach, effectiveness, extensibility, and sustainability of the project results.

In fact, the main characteristics guiding the design of the D&C Plan will be:

- **Reach:** reaching the target groups in Europe and possibly all over the world;
- **Effectiveness:** using effective tools, methods and language for communicating with the targeted stakeholder groups;
- **Extensibility:** allowing the D&C tools wide diffusion in terms of geographical area coverage and size of the involved stakeholders;
- **Sustainability:** making the communication and dissemination infrastructure to function long after the completion of the project.

In support for these issues three important principles will be taken into account:

- 1) All of the project outcomes are elements for communication and dissemination material (in line with the IPR conditions agreed by the partners and with the principles of the Data Management Plan);
- 2) Communication and dissemination actions are ongoing activities for the entire duration of the project;
- 3) All the beneficiaries are involved and take part in the D&C activities, as promoters of a specific action or as contributors to the initiative proposed inside the WP7 by other partners;

All the relevant products and processes developed as intermediate results during the project life-cycle will be considered for D&C activities. Intermediary results play a key role in contributing to achieve the final objectives and impact, and therefore are relevant content for communication and dissemination actions independently from the final outputs of the project. However, some outputs may not be suitable for dissemination, either because they are intended for partners' use only or because their content makes them inappropriate for dissemination. Results and information will be carefully analysed before dissemination through the selected D&C channels.

2.1 Exploitable Knowledge

An important issue when designing the D&C Plan is to understand from the beginning the type of output that will result from the project. To this end, the project outputs will be classified in two main types:

- **Knowledge, know-how and experience:** this type of results is suitable for dissemination to the scientific community through scientific publications, conference presentations as

well as to professional stakeholders that might be interested in best practices and experience gathered from the demonstration activities during the project. All the project management and communication solutions fit this category.

- **Hard Outputs:** this type of results consists of the technological components and/or the full NEWELY system that will be of interest to industrial stakeholders in the hydrogen and energy sector, as well as to SMEs and companies operating in the field of electrolysers technologies.

2.2 D&C Timeline

Figure 1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation timeline

Figure 1 shows the planned timeline regarding the D&C and Exploitation activities. In comparison with the main WP7 milestones and objectives as planned in the Grant Agreement, D&C activities are timely characterized by different phases that could be summarized in two main processes:

- The **INFORMATION** process is characterized by the use of unidirectional communication channels to increase visibility of the project and awareness of the stakeholders and EU society on the NEWELY topics;
- The **DISSEMINATION & COMMUNICATION** process is characterized by the use of bidirectional communication channels that allows the interaction with the targeted stakeholders and a more effective action to collect interest for the exploitation of the project results.

These two processes will be supported by the selected tools and instruments as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Communication process

At the end of the project, as shown in Figure 3, the D&C activities will converge to the main communication channel (i.e. the website) that will remain open after the end of the project. The website will be updated by FBK at least for the next 12 months by the end of the project. Additional press releases and scientific publication could be published by each partner in order to disseminate the final results also after the project completion planned at M36.

Figure 3 D&C Plan at the end of the project

2.3 Deliverables, communication rules and agreements

It is worth recalling that the EC definition of dissemination is “the disclosure of knowledge by any appropriate means other than publication resulting from the formalities for protecting knowledge”. This obligation is qualified by highlighting the importance of ensuring that dissemination does not adversely affect the protection or use of the knowledge generated and, in all cases, dissemination must safeguard Intellectual Property Rights, confidentiality, and the legitimate interests of the parties.

The deliverables that are prepared as documents during the duration of the project must be considered as knowledge of the project and therefore the right to use them needs to be clearly defined for all participants. The issue of ownership of the written reports/documents are addressed herein.

Under copyright law, the author or authors of a work must agree to the copying and dissemination of the work. An important point to note is that the protected work itself may be used without permission as long as this use does not involve copying or dissemination. Therefore, the same access rights as apply to other pre-existing know-how and knowledge within this project also apply to written deliverables and reports that a participant intends to copy or disseminate outside the project.

Deliverables within the project have pre-defined dissemination categories (see GA):

- PU: Public (without restriction, therefore available to all for communication, dissemination and use);
- PP: restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services);
- RE: restricted to a group specified by the Consortium (including the Commission Services);
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

These categories ensure that the Intellectual Property Rights referenced within the Deliverables are protected pending adequate IPR protection and/or that the know-how or trade secrets or other confidential information referenced therein are guaranteed inside the consortium until a final common IP agreement is defined. It is important to note that Confidential Information or information that may be eligible for IP protection cannot regain the confidential status nor the right to IP protection once disclosed publicly.

2.4 Horizon Result Booster Programme

The NEWELY project will benefit from the Horizon Result Booster programme (HRB) of the European Commission. Since November 2020, the NEWELY Consortium joined the PRETZEL, ANIONE and CHANNEL projects to form a Project Group addressing water electrolysis technologies. Starting from 2021, the Project Group will collectively perform D&C activities to strengthen dissemination of water electrolysis technologies and to increase engagement of key stakeholder with the common goal of promoting knowledge of AEWME technologies.

In December 2020, the Project Group has benefited from the HRB Service A - “Portfolio Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy (PDES)” – and specifically from MODULE A: “Identification and creation of the portfolio of R&I project results”. This deliverable will report part of the results deriving from Module A, disclosing information only on the NEWELY project and not on the other Project Group members.

In February 2021, the Project Group will together apply to Module B: “Portfolio dissemination plan design and execution” to design joint dissemination plan with the partner projects, to prepare materials for joint D&C activities, to improve capacity building, to draft a policy brief and to draft a joint social media plan.

3 Stakeholder analysis

Stakeholders are parties that will be affected by operations, objectives and results of the NEWELY project. Stakeholders are categorised and mapped according to several different perspectives including their geographical broadness, domains, type of activity, interest in the portfolio of results, and level of influence.

The stakeholder analysis has been performed by the HRB service provider using the information collected from the questionnaire results and the conference call with the Project group. The primary stakeholders for NEWELY are identified below in order of importance and relevance to the dissemination objectives of the group. As anticipated in the introduction, the D&C activities of the NEWELY project target selected stakeholder groups at different geographical (audience scope) and sectorial levels (target groups).

3.1 Primary stakeholder target group

The main stakeholder group includes start-up and SMEs in the engineering and technology domain at EU level. The group comprises users of electrolyser components as well as suppliers of electrochemical components beyond electrolysis technologies. The number in brackets refers to the portfolio of exploitable results which will be presented in the exploitation plan (D7.3).

Table 2 Primary stakeholder target group

	Stakeholder group
Description	Start-up and SMEs in the engineering and technology domain at EU level
How the STK group can benefit from the NEWELY project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NEWELY prototype will be a new product for producing hydrogen from water electrolysis, with a reduced cost and environmental impact (R11) Disseminate development of AEM and ionomers with increased conductivity and stability to accelerate implantation of AEM electrolysis (R8) Reduction in the use of raw materials will lead to a reduction of costs and environmental impacts. (R13) Development of 2kW AEM stack at low CAPEX will reduce cost of clean H₂ and that will accelerate widespread adaptation of AEM (R14)
Engagement to date	Neutral (Aware of projects yet neither supportive nor resistant)

3.2 Secondary stakeholder target group

The second stakeholder group includes large enterprises in the engineering and technology domain at global level. The group comprises both large companies interested in producing AEM

water electrolyser and companies of similar electro-chemical materials operating in another technological sectors such as mobility, aerospace, filter technology, hydraulic sector. The number in brackets refers to the portfolio of exploitable results which will be presented in the exploitation plan (D7.3).

Table 3 Secondary stakeholder group

	Stakeholder group
Description	Large enterprises in the engineering and technology domain at global level
How the STK group can benefit from the NEWELY project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accelerate innovation and development of AEM electrolyser technology and other applications requiring non-PGM catalysts (R7) Disseminate development of AEM and ionomers with increased conductivity and stability to accelerate implantation of AEM electrolysis (R8) Water electrolysis; Hydrogen; HRS Grid-service; Renewable power sources (R9; R10) Development of 2kW AEM stack at low CAPEX that will reduce cost of clean H₂ and that will accelerate widespread adaptation of AEM (R14)
Engagement to date	Neutral (Aware of projects yet neither supportive nor resistant)

3.3 Tertiary stakeholder target group

The third stakeholder group includes the research and academia in the engineering and technology domain at EU level. The group comprises researchers in the fields of hydrogen technologies, energy engineering, electro-chemistry, chemistry. The number in brackets refers to the portfolio of exploitable results which will be presented in the exploitation plan (D7.3).

Table 4 Tertiary stakeholder group

	Stakeholder group
Description	Research and Academia in the engineering and technology domain at EU level.
How the STK group can benefit from the NEWELY project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardized testing protocol to allow direct comparison of results generated across the globe (R4) Potential new patents on membranes & dispersions (R5) Increased fundamental understanding of electrode design and fabrication for AEM electrolysis (R6) New experimental results will provide new knowledge on the performance and environmental impact of AEMWE technologies. (R12) New development of AEM and ionomers with increased conductivity and stability to accelerate implantation of AEM electrolysis (R8) Accelerate innovation and development of AEM electrolyze technology and other applications requiring non-PGM catalysts (R7)
Engagement to date	Neutral (Aware of projects yet neither supportive nor resistant)

3.4 Stakeholder relevance analysis

The HRB's report "D1.1 Result Portfolio" provides an in-depth analysis of the relevance of the identified stakeholder groups. The influence and interest of each stakeholder group is considered in order to define their strengths in terms of supporting the uptake of the project results. This will help the NEWELY Consortium to understand where to invest effort to maximise dissemination activities, together with the Project Group partners.

Figure 4 Influence vs Interest Grid

- **Players:** the stakeholders falling into this quadrant hold maximum power and express the greatest interest on the project group's results. Large enterprises, Start-ups and SMEs represent the priority target for the NEWELY Consortium to be addresses in order to boost impacts of results through dedicated dissemination activities.
- **Subjects:** the stakeholders falling into this quadrant hold high interest but low power. These stakeholders are represented by Research & Academia, who are highly interested into the project group's results but bear little influence on unleashing the uptake of project group's results. However, engagement of this stakeholder group is still relevant to enhance the future development of AEMWE technology and must be addressed with targeted messages and channels.

3.5 Geographical dimension and level of engagement

The communication and dissemination activities will be performed considering different geographical dimensions. Figure 5 maps the stakeholders according to geographical dimension and current levels of engagement.

Figure 5 Geographical dimension vs. level of engagement

- International Level:** The project results are relevant to the international community operating in hydrogen production, using water electrolysis technology. Substantial effort will be made to sustain and capitalise the interest on how the NEWELY system can compete with the alternatives for hydrogen production currently available on the market. It must be noted, though, that although the interest in the topic can be considered global, one of the barriers refers specifically to the difficulty of bridging the national regulatory differences for the implementation of such technologies.
- European Level:** it is the most significant level for the project D&C activities. One very practical reason for this is that the majority of organisations involved in the projects are European organizations and have therefore an interest in this geographical dimension. From a more general point of view it is also to be considered that the production of green hydrogen, in particular through AEM electrolysis, is now on the forefront of many countries' agenda and therefore the theme of the project can be considered relevant for organisations and institutions on a very large scale
- National (and Regional) Level:** it is essential that project partners carry out dissemination activities in their own countries and within their reach of influence in order to secure national support on different levels with a medium to long term perspective of implementing the NEWELY results;

- **Personal Level:** All key personnel who are directly affiliated with the NEWELY project in the partner institutions are encouraged and expected to put personal effort to promote awareness, understanding and utilization of the project outcomes through individual networking resources.

With the analysis of the current state of engagement and importance of the stakeholders, the right dissemination channels can be identified and used in the Dissemination and Communication Plan.

4 Barriers and Opportunities

This section analyses the main barriers and opportunities to successful D&C actions that have been identified and discussed with the HRB Service providers. The recommendations and outcomes of the analysis have been used as the basis of the NEWELY's D&C Plan.

Table 5 Barriers to dissemination

Barrier	Stakeholder group	Description	Comment
B1	Start-up and SMEs	Dissemination is not widely implemented to start-ups and other SMEs	It's important to expand beyond the existing industry contacts of the projects Consortium in order to find new investors for the next implementation phases of the technologies. A starting point is the use of the dissemination network provided by the HRB. Additionally, participations in third-party events and conferences can simplify the process of outreaching the significant players of the field.
B2	Start-up and SMEs, Large enterprises	Engaging the right stakeholders, while ensuring that IPRs are protected	A good IPR strategy is vital where a new technology is being developed or where old technology is being significantly improved. Application to Module C of the HRB Service 1 can be of help in designing such strategy.
B3	Start-up and SMEs, Large enterprises	Considering the possible barriers linked to the acceptance of the project results.	The acceptance barriers can be divided into two main categories: public acceptance regarding the use of hydrogen and standardization frameworks or legislation differences for hydrogen production in member states. While communication and dissemination campaigns aimed both at SMEs and large enterprises and at the general public are vital to address the first category, a positive engagement of policy makers can benefit both categories by improving the public's opinion and facilitating the implementations of technologies across borders.

Considering the stakeholder analysis presented in Section 3 and the barriers, Figure 6 maps the opportunities for engaging stakeholders with the most appropriate dissemination channel to use to create the greatest impact.

Table 6 Dissemination opportunities

Channel	STK 1 Startups and SMEs	STK 2 Large enterprises	STK 3 Research & academia
Videos	Yes	Yes	
Website	Yes	Yes	Yes
Social media		Yes	
Press releases			Yes
Collaterals: Flyers, banners, posters	Yes	Yes	Yes
Events and workshop	Yes	Yes	Yes
Presentations		Yes	Yes
Datasets and insights		Yes	Yes
Policy Briefs		Yes	
Scientific Papers			Yes

5 Communication Plan

Communication actions will be performed using different communication channels and tools according to the type of stakeholder target group and the desired engagement level. Figure 6 provides an overview of the communication activities and channels that are planned for the NEWELY's project.

Figure 6 Communication Plan

The first ten months of the project have been focused on developing and setting up the tools and channels that will be used for the communication activities during the entire project. Special attention has been paid to developing the visual identity, the website, the social media and the infographics that will distinguish the NEWELY project. The channels will be constantly updated with news on the project (website and social media) whereas the tools will be flexibly used as building blocks for designing further communication materials (e.g. the graphics will be used in posters for scientific conferences). In fact, the main communication tools will be periodically complemented with new materials reporting the updates on the project. Press releases and magazine journals will be published periodically to communicate the main project achievements and emerging innovation.

An omni-channel communication strategy will be used as a cross-channel content strategy to engage and build relationships with targeted audience across multiple points of contact. Communication channels and their supporting resources are designed and orchestrated to cooperate. The coming paragraphs will build upon the information already published in Deliverable D7.1 to describe how the tools, channels and strategies will be used in the communication activities of the NEWELY project.

5.1 Visual identity

The visual identity characterizes all the D&C activities. It comprises the logo, imagery, typography, colours, and creative design that characterize the NEWELY project with a distinguishable brand. The visual identity captures and conveys the symbolic meaning of the project and its targeted technology, while expressing its ambitions, content and characteristics. The visual identity has been used for designing the project's website, social media pages and dissemination materials. It is the branding for the NEWELY's project.

Figure 7 Logo and visual identity

5.2 Project website

The website design of the NEWELY's project has been finalised at M6 by FBK in collaboration with an external communication agency. The website will be updated on a monthly basis with content collected from the partners. The uploaded content will be synergic to the content published on social media. The website will tell "the NEWELY's story" through a storytelling approach that will be developed during the project.

Figure 8 Website

5.3 Communication materials

Communication materials including brochures, posters and a roll-up has been produced at M10. The materials will be used in all communication activities to promote the NEWELY's project. The materials will be updated in the second half of the project with relevant results, focusing on the start-ups and SMEs' group of stakeholders.

Figure 9 Brochure

5.4 Video

At M12, the NEWELY's project video will be released to increase the engagement of the targeted stakeholder groups. The video has been designed in graphic motion to explain the innovativeness of the NEWELY's prototype. The video will be "break-up" in five small video-pills to share on social media.

5.5 Press releases

Press releases will be organized to communicate key project achievements. The main press release is expected at the end of the project (M36) when the project's results will be presented at the final dissemination event.

5.6 Articles on magazines and non-scientific journals

Articles on sectorial magazines and non-scientific journals will be written to periodically communicate the NEWELY project to professional communities and to generic audiences. Among the targeted magazines, there are the partner's magazines (e.g. [FBK Magazine](#)) and the dissemination magazines of the EC (e.g. [Research*EU Magazines](#)). Other magazines include online journals and blogs in the energy and hydrogen sectors as well as local newspapers. Table 7 reports the articles published on online magazines and journals.

Table 7 List of published articles on magazines

Date	Type	Title	Journal	Target	Partners
26 July 2020	Journal Publication	Vodík bude hrát klíčovou roli v dosahování klimatické neutrality	Technical Weekly (CZ)	Industrial stakeholders , scientific community, general public	UCTP

5.7 Social Media

Social media are very effective in attracting the interest of the multiple stakeholders and in actively participating to the latest discussion on hydrogen technologies and policies. The NEWELY's project has activate two social media channels:

- A LinkedIn page of the Project → achieve wide EU citizens stakeholders
- A Twitter profile of the Project → achieve political and industrial stakeholder.

The LinkedIn page and Twitter profile will be in charge of FBK, which will settle the accounts and manage the periodic editorial plans. Partners are invited to follow the NEWELY profiles on social media and re-post the twits/posts on their institutional or personal profiles.

5.8 Other Media

Other media channels (videos, TV/Radio Interview, Newspapers, Podcasts, Blogs, etc.) might be used to communicate about the NEWELY project. Each action will be reported in the updated version of this deliverable.

6 Dissemination Plan

Figure 10 Dissemination Plan

The dissemination plan complements and connects to the communication plan. The plan will be refined at M13 with the input deriving from the HRB Module B dedicated to cross-project dissemination activities. The dissemination plan will be fine-tuned with the plans of the ANIONE and CHANNEL projects in order to carry out common dissemination activities that can strengthen awareness and stakeholder engagement in AEMWE technologies.

The following sections provide the main dissemination activities identified for the NEWELY's project. Whereas the starting of the communication activities is scheduled for the beginning of the project, dissemination activities will begin mostly after M12. Given that dissemination consists in sharing research results with potential users (peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers), one year is the minimum time necessary to collect, analyse and publish relevant results. The dissemination activities are clustered in five types: scientific publications, international conference and workshops, educational activities, exploitation workshops and final dissemination event. Details on each type of activities are provided in the next sections.

6.1 Educational activities

The NEWELY's research partners plan to organize courses and seminars on the main topics of the project, targeting PhDs, university students and high-school students. The purpose of educational activities is to raise interest among students in water electrolysis technologies and to provide a concrete example of applied research in the hydrogen production and energy sector.

Table 8 reports the educational activities planned by the Consortium's partners and the estimated number of engages stakeholders.

Table 8 List of undertaken and planned educational activities

Partner	Date	Type of educational activity	Title	Target audience	Tool used	Links
CEA	2020	Master student internship	Characterization of MEAs for AEM WE	Students	Internship	
CEA	2021	Master student internship	Investigations of additives in MEA AEM WE for improving the performances	Students	Internship	
FBK	03-04/2021	Lectures to students of professional training school	Overview of hydrogen production technologies	Students of professional training schools	Online and face-to-face lectures	http://www.enaiprentino.it/content/tecnico-superiore-energia-e-lambiente
IMC-CAS	05/2021	Master students lectures	Synthesis and characterization of membrane materials	Master students	Oral presentation	https://www.imc.cas.cz/en/
KIST	08/2021	Master thesis 1	TBD	Students	Thesis	www.ust.ac.kr
KIST	02/2023	Master thesis 2	TBD	Students	Thesis	www.ust.ac.kr
UCTP	2020 - 2023	Bachelor and Master lectures	Hydrogen and membrane technologies	Bachelor and Master students	Lectures	https://fcht.vscht.cz/studies

6.2 Scientific publications

Scientific publications represent one of the most important dissemination tools to share research result in the scientific communities and contribute to advance science in general. The NEWELY Consortium targets international scientific communities in the fields of AEMWE, electrolysers, hydrogen production and storage technologies for the mobility and energy sector. In order to contribute to advance the state of the art in these fields, the NEWELY consortium aims at presenting and publishing key scientific results emerging from the project in international scientific journals. Table 9 presents the list of published and foreseen scientific publications, the working papers and the conference proceedings published by the consortium partners. The table will be updated during the project periodic reporting.

Table 9 List of published and planned scientific publications

Date	Type	Title	Journal	Doi	Partners
31 July 2020	Scientific publication	Overview: State-of-the-art commercial membranes for anion exchange membrane water electrolysis	Journal of Electrochemical Energy Conversion and Storage	https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4047963	KIST, DLR, UTCP, IMC-CAS
31 Dec 2021	Scientific publication	Publication about NEWELY catalyst development and characterization	TBA		CENmat, UTCP
2021 (planned)	Conference proceeding	AEM electrolysis at pH7 – status, new developments and perspectives	Proceedings of the Conference EFCF2021		DLR
2022 (planned)	Scientific publication	AEM electrolysis improvements due to PLT and MPL	Peer-reviewed Journal		DLR
2022 (planned)	Scientific publication	AEM electrolysis advances – learnings from the project NEWELY	Peer-reviewed journal		DLR
2022 (planned)	Scientific publication	AEM electrolysis: on the influence of the electrode preparation onto the cell performances	Peer-reviewed journal		CEA

6.3 International conferences and workshops

In order to present the research results to the targeted scientific communities, the NEWELY's partners will attend international scientific conferences and workshops. The main goal of this activity will be to disseminate the project results, obtain feedback on the presented results and identify potential opportunities for collaboration with other researchers and stakeholders operating in the targeted field. Table 10 presents the list of international conferences, external seminars and workshops attended by the Consortium from M1 to M12 and the planned activities for the second project year.

Table 10 List of planned international conferences, external seminars and workshops

Date	Type of event	Title	Target audience	Tool used	Links	Partners
24-25 March 2021	Presentation at Hydrogen Days 2021, online event	High performance alkaline water electrolyser with highly porous non-noble metal	Scientific Community	Presentation	hydrogendays.cz	DLR

		electrodes produced by air plasma spraying (DLR)				
April 2021	Presentation at 29 th Topical Meeting of the International Society of Electrochemistry	Synthesis and characterization of selenide-based catalyst for oxygen reduction reaction in alkaline fuel cells	Scientific community	Poster	https://topical29.ise-online.org/	UCTP
13-17 June 2021	12 th Symposium on Electrochemical Engineering (ESEE 2021)	Preparation of catalyst coated membrane for alkaline water electrolysis: influence of the substrate and preparation method	Scientific Community	Poster	http://www.electrochemical-engineering.eu/2021/	UCTP
22-24 June 2021	Presentation at workshop	TBD	Researchers from academia and industry	Poster	www.emea-workshop.de	KIST, DLR
26 - 30 June 2022	Presentation at WHEC 2022 World Hydrogen Energy Congress in Istanbul	AEM electrolysis at pH7 – focus on the electrode	Scientific Community	Presentation planned by CEA	https://whecistanbul.org/	CEA, DLR, CENMat
29 June 2021	Presentation at EFCF2021 European conference on Low Temperature Fuel Cells, Electrolysers and H ₂ processing	AEM electrolysis at pH7 – status, new developments and perspectives	Scientific Community	Presentation planned by DLR	Efcf.com	DLR

6.4 Exploitation workshops

Two exploitation workshops will be organized as dissemination activities to identify the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) emerging from the project and to select patterns for future exploitation. The exploitation workshops target internal and external stakeholders. The first workshop is scheduled between M20 and M24. It targets internal stakeholders with the objective of characterising the KERs, identifying new results, drafting business models for the selected KERs, assessing the risks and barriers to exploitation. The second exploitation workshop targets external stakeholders with the objective of presenting the KERs in a way that can lead to future collaboration, projects or direct exploitation.

6.5 Final webinar

A final dissemination event in the form of a webinar will be organized at the end of NEWELY to share the final results of the project. The workshop will present NEWELY's main achievements to key stakeholders at the industrial and political level that can contribute to foster the application of the NEWELY technology in the hydrogen production sector and its market upscale. The WP7 Teams will consider the possibility to organize the final webinar in collaboration and agreement with the research and industry groups of FCH JU and other initiatives in the hydrogen production sector.

7 Conclusion

This document presented the Dissemination and Communication Plan for the NEWELY project. Following the definition and agreement of common communication principles, the document presents in detail the activities that will be undertaken by the Consortium during the three years of project.

This document is strictly related to the Deliverable D7.3 – “Exploitation Plan”. The dissemination and communication activities will be performed with the main objectives of supporting the engagement of the identified stakeholder groups that can be interested in exploiting the NEWELY results. Opening future exploitation venues will make NEWELY an important technology for the transition towards a low-carbon hydrogen production and hydrogen economy.